

Rail Surface Defect Detection and Location Based on Image Processing

Altantsetseg Davaakhuu^{1*}, Dong Hua Jun¹

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Dalian Jiaotong University, Dalian 116028, China

Abstract: In recent years, railways have become an important means of transportation for the country, bringing great convenience to the masses and promoting the economic development of the country. These rails play a crucial part in the train operating.

The detection of rail surface defects is vital for high-speed rail maintenance and management. The CNN-based computer vision approach has been proved to be a strong detection tool widely used in various industrial scenarios. However, the CNN-based detection models are diverse from each other in performance, and most of them require sufficient training samples to achieve high detection performance. Selecting an appropriate model and tuning it with insufficient annotated rail defect images is time-consuming and tedious. With an aim of conquering the challenge, stimulated by ensemble learning which employs the multiple learning algorithms so as to obtain greater predictive performance, we create one ensemble framework for detecting the industrialized rail defect.

As well as image augmentation operation, feature augmentation operation is adopted to deeply get the model more diverse at random. A shared feature pyramid network is adopted to reduce model parameters as well as computation cost. Experimental results substantiate that the approach out-performs single detecting architecture in our specified rail defect task. On the collected dataset with 8 defect classes, our algorithm achieves 7.4% higher mAP.5 compared with YOLOv5 and 2.8% higher mAP.5 compared with Faster R-CNN.

Keywords: Railway track line defect, Rail surface defect segmentation, deep learning, YOLOv5

*Corresponding Author: Altantsetseg Davaakhuu, Dong Hua Jun

Accepted: 08 May, 2023; **Published:** 13 May, 2023

How to cite this article: Altantsetseg Davaakhuu, Dong Hua Jun (2023). Rail Surface Defect Detection and Location Based on Image Processing. *North American Academic Research*, 6(5), 21-25. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7932621>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

In the high-speed railway system, the rail plays a dual role of carrying and guiding the running of the train. Its performance straightforward impacts the security of the railway transportation. Therefore, the steel rail is required to be clean and free of surface defects. However, surface defects are inevitable, initiated by degradation, temperature differences, fatigue loading, and foreign objects between the wheel and rail during train operation ^[1, 2], then propagated by means of reduplicative extrusion resulting from the contact pressure between wheels and rails ^[3]. If not detected at an early stage, rail surface defects can result in rapid deterioration and possible failure incurring high maintenance costs.

Early rail surface defect detection relies on manual inspection, which is inefficient and inadequate to meet the advanced high-speed railway industry [4]. Later detection methods include nondestructive evaluation (eddy current, ultrasonic wave, or acoustic emission^[5]), time-frequency analysis [6], vision-based approaches [7-9], and the combination of the above [10].

Recently, the wave of artificial intelligence (AI) is in the ascendant, and the Technology of machine vision is valued. Counting on the task performing, that Techniques is capable of being split into two sorts: object detection and semantic segmentation. In the process of energy technology development, target detection as a related basic research link, making good further learning networks frequently known in research on the construction has also slowly received widely attention inside academic circles. The current research shows that the target detection model for orbital foreign objects Mainly divided into 2 categories. One is the RCNN series, the purpose of which is Target detection is divided into two actions: the first action is to choose the status of the candidate target, The next action is to categorize and refine the candidate objectives. RCNN network, the real-time performance (RT performance) of the model detection is not high, while the exploration of the track foreign objectives demands RT performance. The other type is the single target recognition model, which mainly includes YOLO series and SSD series. This method does not need to identify the candidate area, and directly determines the probability of the target category through the regression coordinates and location. However, existing studies have pointed out that the SSD network is and concentrated foreign object detection are not effective, and the types of foreign objects on the track are also Messy and disorganized, both big and small goals coexist. From the above, it can be seen that based on the Both the RCNN network model and the SSD-based network model have certain limitation. In paper, the deep learning algorithm model based on YOLOv5 Applied to the design of the optimal track foreign object intrusion detection model, in the precondition of guaranteeing efficiency and accuracy, the intrusion of orbital foreign objects can be carried out Better detection, and can play a role in timely warning.

A railway track line image contains a track and two fasteners is shown as in Fig. 1, in which the track fasteners fix the track on the ballast bed.

Fig.1 The railway track line structure

Fig.2 Defects of railway track.

(a) missing fastener and broken fastener; (b) rail corrugation.

As for the railway track lines, their defects largely contain three categories: broken buckle, missing buckle and rail corrugation, as depicted inside Figure 2 (a) and Figure 2 (b) separately.

YOLOv5 algorithm principle

The YOLOv5 model was published by Jocher in June 2020 proposed. Jocher updated YOLOv5 on the basis of studying YOLOv3. The initial version of YOLOv5 is very fast, efficient and easy to use.

Although YOLOv5 is not proposed on the basis of previous YOLO models, novel model system or structural improvement, but YOLOv5 still improves the latest level of target detection methods. And the PyTorch framework used in this paper is a new training deployment framework introduced by YOLOv5, which makes the custom model training more time-sensitive.

The research shows that the YOLOv5 network structure consists of three main components composition, which can be expressed separately as follows.

- (1) Backbone: Aggregate and form different image fine-grained Convolutional Neural Networks for Image Features.
- (2) Neck: a series of networks that mix and combine image features layer, and pass the image features to the prediction layer.
- (3) output: predict image features and generate bounding boxes Merge predicted categories.

For YOLOv5, the Backbone, Neck and output of V5s, V5m, V5l, or V5x are all the same. The only difference is It depends on the depth and width settings of the model. Tested on the coco dataset The test results are shown in Figure 3 . the gray broken line is Efficient Det model, and the other four are different network models of the YOLOv5 series. It can be seen from Figure 1 that the accuracy of the YOLOv5s model is small, the model is small, and it is easy to Transplanted, the YOLOv5x model has high precision, large model, and relatively bloated. The YOLOv5s network structure selected in this paper is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3: Test of YOLOv5 weight file

Fig. 4 Schematic diagram of YOLOv5S structure

Implementation of YOLOv5 target detection algorithm

Object detection system performance data set, and YOLOv5 algorithm model Train and evaluate with the data source obtained and the model architecture used.

Experimental results

Based on the machine training results, we used the test data set in this text to conduct an evaluation test. Some of the test results are shown in Figure 5. According to the category probability of each image, it can be accurately classified and has a high recognition rate.

Fig. 5: Test result of YOLOv5

Conclusion

This chapter continues to explore other algorithms for contact surface defect detection. After briefly introducing the use of the YOLOv5 training platform, four pre-training models based on YOLOv5 were downloaded on Github, and a comparative experiment was carried out on the detection effect of the contact surface defects. According to the trade-off between detection speed and detection accuracy, this paper finally selects the YOLOv5 algorithm as the final algorithm for the detection of surface defects in vacuum contacts.

References

- [1] Kishore M, Park J, Song S, Kim H, Kwon SG. Characterization of defects on rail surface using eddy current technique. *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology*. 2019; 33(9):4209–4215. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12206-019-0816-x>
- [2] Kishore M, Park J, Song S, Kim H, Kwon SG. Characterization of defects on rail surface using eddy current technique. *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology*. 2019; 33(9):4209–4215. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12206-019-0816-x>
- [3] Kishore M, Park J, Song S, Kim H, Kwon SG. Characterization of defects on rail surface using eddy current technique. *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology*. 2019; 33(9):4209–4215. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12206-019-0816-x>
- [4] Liang B, Iwnicki S, Feng G, Ball A, Tran VT, Cattley R. Railway wheel flat and rail surface defect detection by time-frequency analysis. *CHEMICAL ENGINEERING*. 2013; 33.
- [5] Toliyat HA, Abbaszadeh K, Rahimian MM, Olson LE. Rail defect diagnosis using wavelet packet decomposition. *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*. 2003; 39(5):1454–1461.
- [6] Park JW, Lee TG, Back IC, Park SJ, Seo JM, Choi WJ, et al. Rail Surface Defect Detection and Analysis Using Multi-Channel Eddy Current Method Based Algorithm for Defect Evaluation. *Journal of Nondestructive Evaluation*. 2021; 40(3):1–12
- [7] Jie L, Siwei L, Qingyong L, Hanqing Z, Shengwei R. Real-time rail head surface defect detection: A geometrical approach. In: 2009 IEEE International Symposium on Industrial Electronics. IEEE; 2009. p. 769–774.
- [8] Taştımur C, Karakoçse M, Akın E, Aydın İ. Rail defect detection with real time image processing technique. In: 2016 IEEE 14th International Conference on Industrial Informatics (INDIN). IEEE; 2016. p. 411–415.
- [9] Zhang H, Jin X, Wu QJ, Wang Y, He Z, Yang Y. Automatic visual detection system of railway surface defects with curvature filter and improved Gaussian mixture model. *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*. 2018; 67(7):1593–1608.
- [10] Y, Gan J, Wang J, Geng Ya, et al. A coarse-to-fine model for rail surface defect detection. *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*. 2018; 68(3):656–666

